

PRESS RELEASE

Launch of MASTER's first Open Call for XR developers to create digital learning solutions for immediate deployment on learning platform

MASTER project is an EU-funded project under Horizon Europe programme, that focuses on utilizing Extended Reality (XR) technologies to enhance the teaching and training of robotics in manufacturing by developing an open XR platform. The project integrates key functionalities, creating safe and flexible robotic environments with advanced interaction mechanisms. By establishing an open platform for the creation and management of XR content in robotics, the project ultimately aims to benefit non-expert programmers to create robotic XR educational content.

The first Open Call (OC1) which will be receiving applications between 18th of March and 31st of May 2024, will centre on creating proven digital learning solutions ready for immediate deployment using XR technology. We will encourage applicants to address specific technical challenges that have been outlined or propose their own challenges within project's scope. This invitation is extended to any organization involved in developing XR-related technologies. The selected organizations will have the opportunity to integrate their technologies in the platform and test them with a wide range of end-users. The goal is to compile a collection of the above technologies, useful for crafting educational scenarios tailored to the industry's needs. These libraries will then be incorporated into the MASTER XR platform, establishing it as the primary resource for XR-based training in manufacturing.

The OCs has been published in the MASTER portal and in the EU Commission Funding & Tenders Portal (F&T). In addition, the project website has a dedicated page for the OC, where all the important dates and communications, including a public webinar to explain the OC objectives and application procedure are available: <https://www.master-xr.eu/open-calls/>. In addition, you can stay up to date on the project's most important communications and events by following the project's [LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter/X](#) pages.

The benefits for the selected proposals of the Open call include:

- Financial support to up to €150,000.
- Technical support from the respective technical partner of the MASTER consortium.
- Business support during the last four months of the experiment execution period.
- Licenses will be provided by VIRTUALWARE to all beneficiaries for the MASTER platform tools, alongside technical support.
- Potential commercialisation agreement with VIRTUALWARE after the end of the project.

MASTER project participants:

1. [Laboratory for Manufacturing Systems and Automation](#) (LMS) – [University of Patras](#) (GR)
2. [Fundacion Tekniker](#) (ES)
3. [Deutsches Forschungszentrum fur Kunstliche Intelligenz GmbH](#) (DE)
4. [Virtualware 2007 SA](#) (ES)
5. [Teaching Factory Competence Centre Upskilling and Training Development and Implementation of Advanced Technologies for the Manufacturing Industry](#) (GR)
6. [Mondragon Lingua – Alecop, Sociedad Cooperativa](#) (ES)
7. [European Science Communication Institute](#) (DE)

Media contact MASTER project	Project Coordinator
<p>Reza Dabirian European Science Communication Institute (ESCI) Bleicherstr. 11 26122 Oldenburg Germany</p> <p>Phone: +49 441 779 222 27 Email: rd@esci.eu</p>	<p>Panagiotis Karagiannis Laboratory for Manufacturing Systems & Automation (LMS) Department of Mechanical Engineering and Aeronautics University of Patras 26504 Patras Greece</p> <p>Phone: +30 2610 91 01 60 Email: karagiannis@lms.mech.upatras.gr</p>